
82. Gaia's galaxy survey

THE PRIMARY OBJECTIVE of the Gaia space astrometry mission is, of course, to characterise the stellar content of our own Milky Way Galaxy.

But passing across the telescope's fields of view as it scans the sky are other objects which can be measured at the same time. Amongst them are more than 150 000 minor bodies of the solar system, and more than 500 000 quasars. For both of these types of object, their (typically) star-like images makes their detection no more complex than (and indeed operationally on-board indistinguishable from) the detection of stars.

Early in the technological study phase of Gaia (in the late 1990s), it also became clear that distant compact galaxies could also be detected, albeit with some revision of the on-board detection and CCD sampling strategies. And it became progressively more evident that there was a strong science case for their inclusion.

To set the scene, I should recall that, even at 20–21 mag, most of the focal-plane CCD pixels are 'empty' of target stars. Indeed, it is a basic principle of the Gaia measurements that all of the CCD pixels are *not* read out and sent to the ground: the penalty for doing so, in terms of CCD read-out noise, and the data volume to be transmitted to the ground, would be prohibitive.

Instead, stars and star-like objects are detected on-board, as they enter the field, by the sky mappers. Above a given signal-to-noise threshold, information on the target's brightness, location, and transverse motion are transmitted to the subsequent focal plane detectors (astrometry, photometry, and radial velocity spectrometer), where only the small region related to the source is read out, and only these 'windows' are transmitted to ground.

THE OPTIMISATION of a detection and sampling strategy for galaxies, i.e. extended objects characterised by faint surface brightness variations, was not at all straightforward. It was the subject of numerous detailed technical reports and iterations, led by Erik Høg, Mattia Vaccari, Frédéric Arenou and Lennart Lindegren. The status at the time of the 2000 Concept & Technology Report was summarised by Vaccari (2002).

Essentially the problem was to optimise three aspects: (i) the angular areas over which the average surface brightness and local sky background values are computed; (ii) the detection area and signal-to-noise limit such that only useful data are transmitted to the ground (and without being swamped by less interesting regions of the Milky Way or the zodiacal light); (iii) a specific sampling scheme for galaxies, providing a trade-off between angular resolution, CCD read-out noise and telemetry volume. As for stars, a larger sample size would yield a smaller error on the mean surface brightness, along with a lower read-out noise and reduced telemetry rate, but also a lower angular resolution.

For example, a typical galaxy of $I = 17$ would be detected about 60% of the time (or some 50 times on average during a 5-year mission) with a signal-to-noise exceeding 4, using a detection area of 2×2 arcsec².

A statistical model of galaxy number density, size and surface brightness distribution, was also developed to characterise the 'typical' faint galaxy to be targeted. Results suggested that there could be about three million galaxies brighter than this limit at more than $\pm 15^\circ$ from the Galactic plane (i.e. where galaxy detection should not be compromised by the high density of stars).

THE ULTIMATE GOAL could never be a survey of *all* galaxies, but rather a high-reliability multi-colour catalogue extending to low Galactic latitudes, and with high-angular resolution (~ 0.18 arcsec) imaging of all sufficiently high-surface brightness galaxies.

The result would represent a homogeneous and well-defined sample for two main purposes: (i) for a statistical analysis of the photometric structure of the central regions of tens of thousands of well-resolved galaxies at an unprecedented angular resolution, and (ii) for the study of the large-scale structure of the local Universe, aiming to further clarify important features such as large filaments, 'walls', and the Supergalactic Plane.

The resulting scientific case occupied two pages of the 100+ pages dedicated to the overall scientific case for Gaia in 2000 (ESA–SCI(2000)4).

DETAILS OF THE final on-board detection and sampling algorithms are given in the paper describing the overall mission (Gaia Collaboration, 2016), and in the DR1 documentation (de Bruijne et al., 2017).

With the adopted detection algorithm, unresolved early-type elliptical galaxies and galaxy bulges are preferentially detected, even with radii of several arcsec, while late-type spiral galaxies, even those with weak bulges, will remain mostly undetected. In any case, the sampling function for resolved galaxies is complicated, since the onboard detection depends on the contrast between any point-like, central bulge and any extended structure, all convolved along the scanning direction.

The on-ground processing is carried out within Co-ordination Unit 4 of the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium. As one of the nine coordination units, this is dedicated to the treatment of three ‘special’ celestial source types observed by Gaia: non-single stars, solar system objects, and ‘extended objects’.

This latter task, of interest here, treats all sources considered to be extended, aiming to classify the sources and to quantify their morphology. It also analyses all sources separately classified as quasars to search for underlying host galaxies, or other features that could disqualify their use in the reference-frame alignment.

THE RESULTS forming part of Gaia DR3 (released on 13 June) are described by Ducourant et al. (2022). Their adopted surface brightness profile fitting ‘pipeline’ works by simulating a large set of two-dimensional image profiles, then iteratively searching for the one that best reproduces the one-dimensional observations.

As they point out, although their future list of quasar candidates will be based on the results of Gaia’s own classification algorithms, such results were not available for the DR3 processing, which used instead their own compilation of quasar candidates from the existing literature. The sky coverage of each of the merged source catalogues being somewhat heterogeneous, their resulting input list is similarly heterogeneous across the sky.

Their starting list of extended sources similarly contained some 1.7 million galaxies with an entry in Gaia DR3. It is reasonably homogeneous across the sky, except in the Galactic plane which is mostly empty. Their distributions in magnitude and colour are shown here.

FOR THE CLASS of known quasars, their light profile model allows the source structure to be decomposed into two components: the central quasar and a possible surrounding host galaxy. The central quasar is expected to be point-like, its apparent angular extent being essentially due to the line spread function of the Gaia instrument. It is modelled by a circular exponential profile with a fixed scale length (39.4 mas, corresponding to the instrument’s line spread function).

Given that the form of the host galaxy is known to be spiral for distant quasars, but could be bulge-dominated for more nearby quasars, their adopted (Sérsic) profile model has the flexibility to represent either.

For 1 103 691 previously known quasars which were analysed in DR3, the great majority (1 031 607) were classified as point-like, either based on their low integrated flux in the astrometric field data, or on the result of the fitting process. The pipeline processing detected a host galaxy around 64 498 of these, some 6%, and they published the surface brightness profiles of the underlying host galaxy for a subset of 15 867 quasars with robust solutions. The distribution of the Sérsic index describing the light profile of the host galaxies peaks at 0.8, with a mean value of 1.9, indicating that their host galaxies are consistent with disk-like morphologies.

The pipeline also analysed 940 887 galaxies, assuming two different model profiles (a ‘de Vaucouleurs’ profile $\propto r^{1/4}$, and a Sérsic profile $\propto r^{1/n}$) and provided robust solutions for 914 837. In contrast to the underlying quasar hosts, the distribution of the Sérsic indices confirms that Gaia indeed detects mostly elliptical galaxies, and that very few disks are detected.

Ducourant et al. (2022)

WHILE ANY SCIENTIFIC interpretation is a subject for the future, we can only be impressed by the promise of the present results, both in terms of pure numbers, and in the robustness of the profile fitting.

Looking to the future, and in particular to Data Release 4, the number of transits per source will double compared to the data interval used for Gaia DR3, with a corresponding improvement in angular coverage. As a consequence, it is expected that the starting source lists will be at least twice as large as the present ones.

The input list will also improve, complemented by the classification treatment supplied by the relevant DPAC classification unit.

Ducourant et al. (2022)